

GRAMMATICAL ASPECT OF STUDYING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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The transition to interactive methods of learning English grammar is designed to ensure closer interaction of students with each other in the learning process.

Using interactive learning, we strive to involve all students in the process of learning English grammar, to enable students to exchange knowledge, ideas, ways of activity, to think critically, to make informed decisions. Interactive learning methods: project method, role-playing game, business game, brainstorming, discussions, case study, collaborative learning.

Teaching experience shows that master's grammar training is an important component of the educational process: high-quality knowledge of English. The integrity of the statement depends on the knowledge of the specifics of English grammatical constructions. Knowledge of language material is subject to further training, namely, observation of the grammar phenomenon in the text or specially selected sentences, practical use of grammar material in speech through multiple training and automation of the use of the language phenomenon in speech. It is necessary to fix the rules by repeating the same type of phrases that cause a certain systemic in the brain.

Learning through text gives the opportunity to learn new lexical or grammatical material, learn to communicate, creating communicative situations based on the text. Insufficient time does not allow other approaches to be used for wider study of a foreign language. Therefore, this method is very productive in a non-language technical university. The communicative purpose of grammar learning allows forming a basic requirement for the amount of grammar material to be learned.

Thus, the optimal result in the learning process will be achieved by combining mechanical memorization of rules-formulas and conscious use of appropriate grammatical forms in certain situations. Particular attention is paid to the theory using clarity, its optimal combination with language practice.

The prospect of further research is to find out the factors that contribute to the analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of methods of learning foreign language grammar in the conditions of technical higher education.